

THEORETICAL AND LEGAL COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE LEGAL NATURE OF A CORPORATE CONTRACT UNDER THE LAW OF FRANCE AND THE USA

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Abstract. The article provides a comparative analysis of theoretical and legal approaches and specific features of corporate agreement regulation under French and US legislation. The spread of mutual agreements between shareholders in France was facilitated by the participation of Anglo-American investors in French companies, who were more accustomed to contractual relations than to the use of strictly fixed forms of joint-stock companies. Despite the fact that one of the goals of such agreements was an attempt to get rid of excessive public-law control, such agreements could never contradict the imperative requirements of the law and the provisions of the company's charter. In the USA, the legislative consolidation of the right of shareholders to enter into various types of agreements among themselves is carried out by laws regulating the activities, procedure for the creation and management of entrepreneurial corporations. The content of and participation in a shareholder agreement is determined by the legal regime of the corporation. An agreement of members of a closed corporation may de facto change the provisions of the charter concerning the management of the corporation and the division of profits. The article considers all types of shareholder agreements concluded by members of an entrepreneurial corporation. State laws governing contractual relations do not apply to shareholder agreements, despite the doctrinal view that corporations are contractual in nature. A comparative analysis of the case law, doctrine, and provisions of the US and French laws leads to the conclusion that in the US, shareholder agreements are governed by corporate law, and not by the provisions of the law of obligations, as in France.

Keywords: corporate agreement, agreement of members of the company, principle of freedom of contract, right to vote, rights of members of the corporation, disclosure of information, trade register, comparative corporate law, confidential information, joint-stock companies, limited liability companies, business corporation, contract law, obligation, civil law contract

The principle of freedom of contract as a sacred foundation of contract law in the European civilistic doctrine of the 19th century acquires particular relevance in modern corporate law. This key principle of the individualistic philosophy of the Enlightenment, further developed in the works of Ch.

Montesquieu, T. Hobbes, J. Locke, J. J. Rousseau, I. Kant, G. Hegel and many other representatives of the classical natural law doctrine, has been discussed by representatives of foreign and domestic science for two centuries. The analysis of principles in the philosophy of law is devoted to the works of Russian researchers - B. N. Chicherin, I. A. Ilyin, N. M. Korkunov. In addition, as R. A. Emrikh rightly notes, "the appeal to the idea of freedom of contract as a principle of justification of law is associated with the fact that modern Russian legal consciousness assimilates a number of ideas (the concept of human rights, civil society, the rule of law), which are born of the world, mainly Western legal culture" . Modern conditions of doing business, globalization, integration, creation of transnational corporations, national and international competition, emergence of new organizational and legal forms of legal entities, widespread use of corporate forms of management have determined the need to find flexible and effective methods of regulating relations between participants of corporations. That is why theoretical and practical comparative study of the legal nature of such a flexible legal instrument as a corporate agreement seems relevant and necessary from the point of view of protecting the rights of participants of corporations and third parties. The idea of concluding an agreement of participants of a company arose as a result of the development of the principle of freedom of contract. In the common law system, before the emergence of judicial practice containing interpretations of agreements of this kind and the further normative institutionalization of agreements of participants, freedom of contract served as the justification for such agreements. In *Brown v. Pacific Mail Steamship Co* (1867) , the court held that the parties were prohibited by the agreement from changing the mandatory provisions of statutory law establishing the system of governance of the company, but the court left the agreement without consideration as to the voting procedure, implicitly upholding its permissibility. Later, in *Faulds v. Yates* (1870) , the court upheld the legality of obligating the parties to vote in a certain way.

Turning to the history of the emergence of corporate agreements in French law, one can notice a strong influence of Anglo-American approaches. In particular, the spread of mutual agreements between shareholders in France was largely facilitated by the participation in French companies of Anglo-American investors, who were more accustomed to contractual relations than to the use of strictly fixed forms of joint-stock companies. Despite the fact that one of the goals of such agreements was an attempt to get rid of excessive public-law

control, such agreements could never contradict the imperative requirements of the law and the provisions of the company's charter.

Current French legislation does not disclose the legal concept of a corporate agreement; in literature and judicial practice, such a general concept as a participant agreement (*les conventions sociétaires*) is used. At the same time, participant agreements concluded in joint-stock companies, simplified joint-stock companies, and limited liability companies have their own characteristics and may have different names.

Traditionally, the conclusion of agreements between members of a company under French law is based on the principle of freedom of contract, taking into account Article 6 of the French Civil Code (hereinafter referred to as the FCC) , according to which laws concerning the fundamentals of morality (*les bonnes moeurs*) and public order (*l'ordre public*) cannot be changed by private agreements, and Article 1193 of the FCC establishes that contracts can be changed or cancelled only by mutual consent of the parties or on grounds permitted by law.

Analyzing the dynamics of the application of shareholders' agreements in France, A. Couret notes that, as a rule, "the legality of mutual agreements between shareholders is not contested (except in cases where they infringe on public law requirements in the area of shareholder law). The real difficulties are connected with the practical application of these agreements. Judges try to encourage such practice, which is evident from the decisions taken. However, at the moment, practical application remains the weak point of agreements between shareholders" .

The widespread use of corporate agreements and the problems of their practical application noted in the doctrine forced French researchers to turn to the study of the legal nature of the agreement of the participants . The doctrine proposed a definition of a mutual agreement of shareholders as an agreement, contract or condition concluded between two, many or all participants of a joint-stock company, the purpose of which is to provide all signatories with the opportunity to obtain or retain their own rights or to organize in one way or another the management body of the company . According to E. A. Sukhanov, corporate agreements under French law are "agreements on the exercise of shareholders' rights, and those concerning mainly or even exclusively the right to vote (*conventions de vote*). In principle, they can only concern the voting of shareholders and only at a specific meeting (and not during any period), and are also subject to other serious restrictions" .

It should be taken into account that under French law, shareholders' agreements of a company whose shares are listed on the stock exchange have their own specific features. Thus, according to Art. L 233-11 of the FTC, the terms of a shareholders' agreement establishing the rights and obligations with respect to the disposal of more than 0.5% of the shares or the right to dispose of 0.5% of the votes of a company whose shares are listed on the stock exchange must be communicated to the company itself and the Financial Markets Authority (AMF).

The evolution of methods for regulating management and relations between participants in a company, using the example of the French experience, allows us to identify not only the tendency to maintain traditional management methods in a joint-stock company, but also the emergence of two new methods: regulation based on an agreement between participants and regulation using recommended norms (soft law).

The legislation of France, as well as many countries with a Romano-Germanic legal system, does not contain any special rules devoted to the regulation of shareholders' agreements. However, such agreements are recognized at the doctrinal and practical levels. As M. V. Trubina rightly notes, in many Western European countries "the thesis that shareholders' agreements do not require special legal regulation is almost universally recognized, and that general rules and principles of civil and shareholders' legislation can be used to determine the admissibility, legality, content and form of shareholders' agreements". The peculiarity of the legal regulation of participants' agreements under French legislation lies in the obligatory nature of such agreements, which do not create obligations for the company itself and the participants who are not parties to the agreements. E. A. Sukhanov believes that "the obligatory-legal nature of such agreements is not questioned: they are ordinary civil-law contracts, and not corporate acts".

Over the past few decades, French researchers have been discussing the theory of the "golden mean" in corporate law, the idea of which lies in the optimal relationship between freedom of contract and public order, and, according to J. Carbonnier, it is freedom of contract that is the legal basis of a market economy.

The main purposes of concluding corporate agreements are to ensure the stability of the company's capital, management and control, to reach an agreement on voting, etc. Despite the fact that a corporate agreement under French law is regulated primarily by the rules on obligations, the legal

consequences of this agreement have specifics, go beyond the civil obligation and are of a corporate nature. In the United States, shareholder agreements are, albeit sparingly, regulated by corporate law.

Legislative regulation of shareholder agreements in the United States also did not appear immediately. The appearance first in entrepreneurial activity, and then in legislation, of agreements of shareholders of an entrepreneurial corporation is due to a number of reasons, but the main reason was the desire of shareholders to participate in the management of the affairs of an entrepreneurial corporation.

In the Uzbek legal reality, the corporate agreement appeared relatively recently, and its appearance in the legislation was caused by other reasons. First of all, it is necessary to define the concepts that Russian legislation and US legislation operate with. In general, they coincide, but the corporate agreement is called a shareholders' agreement by state laws and the uniform law.

It is worth recalling that the structure of business corporation management in the United States does not involve shareholders. All management is concentrated in the hands of the board of directors and the managers appointed by them. Shareholders are completely removed from making operational management decisions and have almost no participation in developing strategic objectives and corresponding decisions. Even before the first state laws regulating the activities of business corporations appeared, according to common law, shareholders only had the right to receive a portion of the corporation's profits in the form of dividends and the right and obligation to form a board of directors. The courts also secured for shareholders the right to make decisions on such fateful issues as the liquidation of a corporation, its merger with another corporation, and the sale of all of the corporation's assets.

Over time, this situation ceased to correspond to the interests of shareholders, since the strict dictate of the board of directors on issues of determining the size of dividends and their payment did not contribute to the growth of shareholders' income. Shareholders could not influence the procedure for distributing the corporation's profits. Absolute lack of rights, the impossibility of influencing the distribution of profits, the unfair behavior of members of the boards of directors and managers, complicated economic relations - all of these factors led to the adoption by state legislators of special laws regulating the activities of entrepreneurial corporations. Later, the states adjusted these laws with the proposed model law on an entrepreneurial corporation.

The developers of the model law took into account the current mood of shareholders and the judicial practice of recognizing agreements concluded by shareholders aimed at increasing their influence on management decision-making. The law now includes provisions securing the right of shareholders to conclude agreements of various natures, as well as provisions characterizing the type of entrepreneurial corporation provided for by law.

Such a type is a closed corporation. The extension of the norms of the model law on entrepreneurial corporations to this corporation confirms the fact that this is not a new type of corporation with qualifying features, but only a type of entrepreneurial corporation. The existence of a closed corporation determined some features of the legal status of this type of entrepreneurial corporation and was reflected in the content of the agreement that shareholders of the corporation have the right to conclude among themselves. Agreements of shareholders of an entrepreneurial corporation and a closed entrepreneurial corporation are aimed at achieving the same goals, but differ greatly in content.

Let's start with the fact that the "general meeting of shareholders" of a corporation is not called the governing body of a corporation by the laws of individual states, as well as the model law on a business corporation. Only in the literature do individual authors sometimes conclude that the general meeting of shareholders makes certain decisions. The terms "competence of the general meeting" or "exclusive competence of the general meeting" are not used in scientific literature and legislation in the United States . The competence of the general meeting of shareholders in legislation is designated as "shareholders' rights" and "rights realized by voting on certain issues". State legislators include the following in the exclusive competence of the general meeting, voting on which may be the subject of agreements in shareholder agreements:

- formation of the board of directors by electing its members;

- increasing the authorized capital of the corporation, if this issue is not referred to the board of directors for decision; development and amendment of the charter and regulations of the corporation;

- leasing, sale or transfer (in the form of reorganization) of all property of the corporation to a third party, approval of unusual, especially large transactions;

- transfer of all property of the corporation to a third party for the purpose of conducting business activities for a period of time;

- corresponding amendments to the charter related to the suspension of business activities, if this entails a change in the scope of shareholders' rights for certain types of shares;

reorganization by merger or through the sale of all assets;
liquidation of the corporation.

The founders have the right to expand the list of issues, the decision on which is taken only by the members of the corporation at their meeting, by the corporation's charter.

As we can see, the shareholders' agreement of a business corporation cannot in any way affect the change in the procedure for managing the corporation by shareholders or allow interference in the procedure for distributing the corporation's profits. Of course, legislators have significantly expanded the rights of shareholders, but this expansion has not brought shareholders closer to managing the corporation. However, such a statement is true only in relation to a business corporation, while for closed corporations a different relationship is established between the provisions of the charter and the shareholders' agreement.

Unlike the shareholders' agreement of a business corporation, the shareholders' agreement of a closed corporation may contain conditions that change the procedure for managing the corporation established by the charter, as well as the procedure for distributing profits. In other words, the provisions of the shareholders' agreement of a closed corporation may change the provisions of the charter of a closed corporation when the procedure for managing the corporation established by the shareholders' agreement does not correspond to what is determined by the charter. At the same time, shareholders of a closed corporation have the right to enter into agreements that do not change the established procedure for management and distribution of profits, i.e., those that concern only the procedure for voting at a general meeting on issues within their competence.

From the above it follows that today state laws provide for several types of shareholder agreements. The content and number of participants in these agreements depend on the shareholders of which corporation are concluding the agreements. At the same time, it is possible to distinguish shareholder agreements available to shareholders of any business corporation. These agreements, in turn, are divided into two types.

The first type of shareholder agreement is an agreement on the procedure for voting at a general meeting on all issues within the competence of the general meeting. The second type of shareholder agreement is an agreement on the transfer of the right to vote at a general meeting by shareholders who have signed the agreement, either to one of the shareholders or to a third party. State

laws call this type of shareholder agreement a "voting trust." In addition to shareholders, other persons may also be participants in this type of shareholder agreement, such as a creditor of the corporation, a trustee of the corporation's shares, or a pledgee of the corporation's shares or bonds. A voting trust is often used to ensure the fulfillment of the corporation's contractual obligations. In all states, the term for which a voting trust may be concluded is limited by law, as is the transfer of shares by shareholders under an agreement to a trust. Concluding a shareholder agreement to transfer the right to vote for a longer term than that established by state law makes this agreement invalid. For example, in the state of California, according to the current legislation, a voting trust is concluded for a term of no more than 10 years.

The third type of shareholders' agreement, provided for by state laws, is available only to shareholders of a closed corporation. It is this type of shareholders' agreement that enables shareholders to change the order of corporation management, establish the order of profit distribution, and limit the powers of the board of directors. State laws contain a list of provisions of the charter that cannot be changed by an agreement of shareholders of a closed corporation. Another feature of this type of shareholders' agreement is the fact that it is concluded only between all members of a closed corporation. It is the participation of all members of the corporation in the agreement that removes the question of the legality of this third type of shareholders' agreement. Mandatory participation of all members of a closed corporation in the third type of shareholders' agreement was provided for by the model law on a business corporation and was not subject to change by state laws when implementing the model law into state legislation. In general, these three types of shareholders' agreements in all states, with some exceptions, are regulated by laws uniformly. In fairness, it should be noted that this regulation is very brief. The stinginess of the legislative regulation of shareholders' agreements is due to the fact that legislators have not yet decided on a contractual model of shareholders' agreements. It is noteworthy that all the rules governing shareholder agreements are included in the laws on business corporations. It is the laws related to corporate law that determine the types, procedure for concluding and terminating shareholder agreements, as well as their terms and relationship with the provisions of the corporation's charter and regulations. Neither the laws governing contractual relations, nor the Uniform Commercial Code, and subsequently the commercial codes of the states, contain any indication of extending their effect to shareholder agreements. The fact is that two

contractual models still coexist in the legislative practice of individual US states. The process of their convergence is intensive, but unification has not yet occurred. Legislators and courts have not yet decided on which contractual model a shareholder agreement is based on. This circumstance largely explains the fact that the provisions of contract law do not apply to shareholder agreements. On the one hand, it is obvious that a shareholder agreement is the result of the coordination of the wills of its participants, without reaching an agreement between whom its conclusion is impossible. This clearly demonstrates the legal nature of the contract as an agreement that complies with the European contractual model, and, consequently, the rules governing business contracts, which are also based on the European contractual model, may apply to it.

On the other hand, neither legislators nor courts yet classify shareholders' agreements as business contracts, much less as contracts of the English contractual model of shareholders' agreement. Let us recall that the English contractual model is a contract based on mutual promises of the parties, supported by judicial protection. We assume that the presence of two contractual models in contract law prevents the full extension of the provisions of the legislation on contracts to the shareholders' agreement, leaving it in the sphere of corporate regulation.

Thus, a comparative analysis of judicial practice, doctrine and provisions of the legislation of the USA and France allows us to draw the following conclusions:

in the USA, shareholders' agreements are regulated by corporate law, and not by the provisions of contract law;

in France, shareholders' agreements are regulated by the provisions of the law of obligations, while the legal consequences of this agreement have specifics, go beyond the scope of a civil obligation and are of a corporate nature.

Based on the above text, several key conclusions can be made regarding the management structure of entrepreneurial corporations in the USA and the role of shareholders in these processes:

1. Removal of shareholders from day-to-day management:

In traditional business corporations, shareholders do not participate in day-to-day management decisions. All management powers are concentrated in the hands of the board of directors and the managers appointed by them. Shareholders can only receive dividends and form the board of directors, but do not influence the day-to-day operations of the company.

2. Historical development of shareholder rights:

Initially, shareholders had limited rights: only the right to receive profits (dividends) and the right to form the board of directors. However, over time, this structure was changed in response to shareholder interests, which led to the creation of laws regulating the activities of corporations and strengthening shareholder rights.

3. Closed corporations as a special case:

Closed corporations, unlike regular business corporations, allow shareholders to have more influence over management and profit distribution. In closed corporations, shareholder agreements can change the corporation's bylaws, including the procedure for management and profit distribution. This difference gives shareholders more control and influence over strategic decisions.

4. Shareholders' Agreements:

US state laws provide for several types of shareholders' agreements, which can vary significantly depending on the type of corporation. For closed corporations, shareholders can enter into agreements that change the established rules for management and distribution of profits, which is not allowed in public corporations. Such agreements can set out terms that allow shareholders to control the voting procedure and manage corporate processes more flexibly.

5. The Role of the General Meeting of Shareholders:

Under US law, the general meeting of shareholders is not considered a corporate governance body, although it decides on important issues such as the election of the board of directors and the approval of major transactions (e.g. mergers, liquidations, and asset sales). It is important to emphasize that for regular corporations, shareholders' rights are limited at this level, and their influence on operational management remains minimal.

6. Prospects for Changes and Development of Shareholders' Rights:

Despite the expansion of shareholders' rights, legislators do not give them full control over the operational management of corporations. This leads to a further division of shareholders' agreements for different types of corporations. For closed corporations, shareholders can influence processes at a higher level, while for entrepreneurial corporations, shareholders remain limited in their influence on management issues.

Conclusion:

Thus, the main conclusions from the text are as follows:

The management system in traditional corporations does not imply active participation of shareholders in operational management, which limits their rights in decision-making.

Closed corporations give shareholders more rights to change the order of management and distribution of profits, which allows them to more effectively control the company's activities.

Shareholder agreements play a key role in changing the legal relations between shareholders, and these agreements can vary significantly depending on the type of corporation.

Legislation continues to evolve, directing shareholders to more active participation in corporate management, especially in closed corporations, but they are still limited in their powers in traditional entrepreneurial corporations.

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